

Study Title:

VALIDATE Workshop Study - Identifying auditable practical trustworthy artificial intelligence requirements for the Horizon Europe VALIDATE study

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SYNOPSIS

Study Title	VALIDATE Workshop Study - Identifying auditable practical trustworthy artificial intelligence requirements for the Horizon Europe VALIDATE study	
Internal ref. no. / short title		
Study Design	Qualitative co-creation workshops	
Study Participants	40-60	
Planned Sample Size	10 workshops with 3-6 participants	
Planned Study Period	January 2023 – February 2023	
	Objectives	Outcome Measures
Primary	What do VALIDATE staff members consider to be key low-level requirements for the use of AI in stroke?	How does the recommended low-level requirements by the VALIDATE staff members compare to assessments from external experts and the results of a Z-inspection assessment?
Secondary	Will the use of co-creation workshops deduce requirements that cannot be mapped to the EU guidelines for Trustworthy AI?	How does the low-level requirements compare with the high-level and mid-level guidelines proposed by the EU?

1. BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

An increasing amount of digital data is available in healthcare. This is a prerequisite for the development of data-driven artificial intelligence (AI) techniques for a range of applications, including monitoring, prognosis, and diagnosis (Topol, 2019).

AI-driven applications have the potential to increase both the effectiveness and efficiency of healthcare to improve patient outcomes and reduce societal and economic burdens, especially in the form of Clinical decision support systems (CDSS). Because of its potential, AI is one of the most effective ways to address two of the biggest problems facing modern medicine: the high incidence of chronic diseases such as cerebrovascular disease and stroke in the ageing population, and the rising cost of medicines (Hood et al., 2022).

However, there are many challenges to the adoption of AI in healthcare.

AI systems are vulnerable to **data bias** (deviation from a balanced representation in terms of, for example, gender, age, skin colour or socio-economic background), potentially leading to unfair applications of tools. The use cases for which AI is researched and developed, the way clinical problems are statistically formulated, the variables included for training, and the design of validation and testing

studies are all influenced by latent biases arising from cognitive biases (Haselton et al., 2015; Leslie et al., 2021; O'Sullivan & Schofield, 2018). Therefore, discriminatory patterns may emerge in the design processes (Leslie et al., 2021).

To identify and mitigate the effects of bias, the goal of **transparency** is introduced in the applied design decisions, the selection of algorithms, the code, and the data. However, the AI systems currently achieving the best performance are often "black box" algorithms, such as deep artificial neural networks (ANN), often featuring million-fold activations between multiple layers, which cannot be displayed in a way comprehensible to humans. Explainable AI (xAI) methods are an active area of research, where some works aim at producing simpler models that approximate the internal workings of ANNs (Rudin, 2019). Some authors claim, however, that these techniques are so unreliable that we should stop using ANNs in healthcare altogether and switch to AI techniques that support inherent interpretability (Rudin, 2019). As a result, there is currently a fierce scientific dispute about the correct terminology, the ethical and legal requirements of explainability, and whether explainability or interpretability is preferable (Amann et al., 2020; Gerke et al., 2020).

Despite the laws and regulations present in most countries to govern **safety** in general, there are still many unresolved issues related to the regulation of AI. When and how should healthcare professionals rely on AI tools? Regarding **accountability**, there is a question of 'epistemic authority', or more specifically, when should a clinician really defer to the system's findings (Grote, 2021; Grote & Berens, 2020)? The question of liability is summarized by Gerke et al. as follows (2020): A doctor would likely be held accountable for medical negligence if they make a misleading diagnosis based on AI. Healthcare professionals will have to use AI tools once they become the norm. What happens in these circumstances? Furthermore, increasing automation may lead to a deterioration in the quality of the doctor-patient relationship (Triberti et al., 2022) and to a reduction in the healthcare workforce (Rafner et al., 2022). The use of these technologies by health professionals would likely be met with hesitation and caution, and the self-image of the medical profession may need to be reviewed.

In summary, there are a number of issues that may significantly reduce the willingness of doctors and patients to adopt AI systems in healthcare (Bouschery, 2021; Gaube et al., 2021; LaRosa & Danks, 2018; Liao & Sundar, 2021; Longoni et al., 2019; Longoni & Morewedge, 2019; Wang & Siau, 2018). Only if doctors and patients have enough trust in AI-based healthcare solutions to use them, will they be able to deliver on their potential and promise. As a result, what may be the most promising technology of recent years is not yet available to most patients in the current healthcare systems.

However, it has been highlighted that despite the proliferation of guidelines on trustworthy AI, there is no shortage of reports on unethical use of AI (Morley et al., 2021). The frameworks currently in use are too abstract to be useful for researchers and developers of AI systems (Morley et al., 2021). AI guidelines are often simple rules based on principles, similar to principlism, the framework Beauchamp and Childress created for bioethics (Beauchamp, 2019; Mittelstadt, 2019). A survey found that more than 80% of the main ethical guidelines offer no or the least amount of practical evidence, and that 75% of them offer only very little practical information (Bélisle-Pipon et al., 2022). Thus, high-level principles are of limited usefulness as they are unable to provide concrete advice and fail to address fundamental normative tensions inherent in important concepts such as fairness or privacy (Mittelstadt, 2019). Most of the frameworks currently in use focus on 'what' should be achieved rather than providing instructions for 'how' it can be achieved in practice (Morley et al., 2020). Furthermore, the frameworks that are intended to provide an answer to the 'how' suffer from serious usability problems, meaning that they

provide only a very limited amount of guidance for practical application (Morley et al., 2020) . As a consequence, ethical considerations are mostly ignored in AI research and it is still unclear how ethical principles can be applied in ethical behaviour (Vakkuri et al., 2020).

Within the Horizon Europe study VALIDATE, we face exactly this challenge.

VALIDATE aims to develop, test, and validate AI-based prognostic tools for acute stroke patient stratification. There is great potential here to go beyond the current clinical state of the art, as AI can excel at finding complex and non-linear relationships between a wide range of prognostic variables. The critical clinical question in this context is: how can stroke treatment outcomes be improved at the individual patient level by using AI methods?

A major obstacle to answer this question is that AI-based prognostic tools and subsequent clinical decision support will only be approved and accepted in the clinical setting if they fulfil all necessary criteria with regards to regulatory, lawfulness, ethics, robustness, and trustworthiness.

As a result, within the Horizon Europe VALIDATE project we aim to follow the high-level and mid-level specifications in the Trustworthy AI Guidelines of the EU (European Commission, 2019).

As previously mentioned, however, the practicality of these guidelines is heavily limited as they are high-level principles. Thus, within the VALIDATE project we will need to derive low-level practical requirements specific to our given use case of clinical decision support in acute stroke. This task is difficult, as there are no established practices of quantifying ethics requirements in a way that makes the progress measurable. Moreover, it can be easier to avoid accountability or to be prone to ethics-washing.

In the context of explainability (which is just one of many requirements), recent work has proposed metrics for the quality of explanations, both from the subjective (Hoffman et al., 2019; Mohseni et al., 2021) and algorithmic (Hedström et al., 2022) points of view. With the exception of some work on explainability, there is a research gap because there are currently no accepted and validated methodology to derive or quantify low-level requirements for an AI system.

We will thus perform a qualitative research study where we use co-creation workshops with the primary goal of determining the low-level trustworthy AI requirements for the VALIDATE AI tool. We will recruit VALIDATE personnel and involve them in a series of co-creation workshops, to identify the aspects of this particular AI tool that are most relevant to trustworthiness. The aim is to co-create and define actionable, low-level practical guidelines for VALIDATE based on information from the VALIDATE personnel. As a secondary goal, we will compare the co-created requirements with the guidelines for Trustworthy AI from the European Commission, particularly the Trustworthy AI Assessment List (2019, p. 26). The comparison will be done to assess whether the workshops were able to deduce requirements outside of the recommendations from the European Commission.

2. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

Research Questions
<p>Primary:</p> <p>What do VALIDATE staff members consider to be key low-level requirements for the use of AI in stroke?</p>
<p>Secondary:</p> <p>Will the use of co-creation workshops deduce requirements that cannot be mapped to the EU guidelines for Trustworthy AI?</p>

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Study Methodology

Co-creation encompasses a wide range of practices for design and decision-making that involve stakeholders and users (Jones, 2018). The strategy of co-creation techniques has existed for quite some time, but nowadays the co-creation method, called crowdsourcing, offers new and powerful possibilities and is used in many fields (Tackx & Verdin, 2014).

In co-creation, relevant stakeholders work together to generate value and meaning, and it has received increasing attention as a method of improving the validity of qualitative research (Jansma et al., 2022). Several scholars have studied the functionality and legitimacy of knowledge, research, and innovation using the concept of co-creation (Engels et al., 2019; Gudowsky & Sotoudeh, 2017). They found the concept of co-creation to be a valuable tool to converge the stakeholders' different backgrounds and perspectives into coherent workshop outcomes. Moreover, co-creation has been proposed as an instrument for enhancing innovation and develop policies for research (Jansma et al., 2022). Stakeholders participate in a collaborative process to generate and develop value in a bottom-up approach including people such as end-users and patients; as opposed to a top-down approach where traditionally more powerful stakeholders (producers, policymakers, engineers, or innovators) are the definers of value (Ind & Coates, 2013).

There is no one unified way of eliciting quality requirements (as opposed to functional requirements) such as ethics. However, workshops have been suggested as a suitable method (Pacheco et al., 2018). It is important to consider the difference of wishes and wants of the stakeholders, and workshops have been concluded to be useful for this purpose (Pacheco et al., 2018). On the other hand, the diverse atmosphere of stakeholders might increase the potential for conflicts and differing viewpoints. The format of workshops will help resolve potential conflicts because they allow stakeholders to effectively negotiate and collaborate (Pacheco et al., 2018). Workshops are effective bidirectional communication tools, and they improve the understanding among the stakeholders (Pacheco et al., 2018).

According to Jansma et al. (2022), co-creation workshops offer many advantages, such as reflexivity. In this context, reflexivity refers to scientists, innovators, and other stakeholders participating in a workshop and reflecting on their day-to-day practices. Workshops that involve co-creation provide an opportunity for the stakeholders to equally share power and thus each can add value according to their interests and skills. (Jansma et al., 2022)

According to Pacheco et al., workshops are effective when wanting to elicit diverse types of requirements from big and complex systems, and the AI tool for our study is a complex system (2018). One of the challenges of ethical requirements in AI is that the different requirements can contradict each other. Workshops have previously been observed to be effective for prioritizing and managing requirements and will hopefully be useful in that regard for our study (Pacheco et al., 2018).

Workshops enable researchers to investigate and identify factors relevant for challenges related to technology that are hard to define (Phaal et al., 2007; Ørngreen & Levinsen, 2017). Workshops have been found to be particularly useful for studies that are emerging, unpredictable, and investigating factors that are not already obvious to the participants or the researchers. It was found that the workshops were able to uncover biases and blind spots of the participants; that similar findings would not have emerged with a different research design; and that the workshops sparked debates that led to a clearer understanding of the problem (Ørngreen & Levinsen, 2017; Ahmed & Asraf, 2018)

In this study, workshops are used as a method to solve the challenge of concretizing high level ethics guidelines. Concretizing high-level ethics guidelines into concrete and measurable practices is somewhat of a hard-to-define challenge that is likely to have unpredictable results, because what is considered ethical can be highly subjective on an individual basis and how this challenge should be solved is not already obvious to neither the participants nor the researchers. Uncovering biases and blind spots is an important part of this solution, and as previously mentioned, the use of workshops can support this.

Since many of the study participants will have a non-technical background, improving their technological literacy is important for them to be able to raise ethical concerns related to the use of AI in a medical setting. The use of workshops is therefore suitable for this study as they have been found to be able to increase the technological understanding of participants (Ørngreen & Levinsen, 2017; Phaal et al., 2007). Additionally, sheets with definitions of some technical terms such as “AI” will be provided to the participants in advance of the workshops.

Despite these advantages, a drawback of co-creation workshops is that they may be impacted by participant hierarchy. Ideas presented by more powerful people are likely to be endorsed more than those presented by less powerful people, e.g., doctors versus patients (Tackx & Verdin, 2014). Additionally, in order to maintain a high degree of research quality when using workshops, the participants’ needs during the workshops are sufficiently addressed (Ørngreen & Levinsen, 2017).

In VALIDATE, our goal is to create a safe and equal environment for knowledge exchange. VALIDATE will therefore use skilled facilitators who can help manage the issue of participant hierarchies, with a particular focus on junior/senior professionals and the use of English as a secondary language. Co-creation workshops in VALIDATE is seen as a collaborative process between the investigators and participants who are seen as experts of their lived experiences, while the investigators still have control of the agenda and final outcomes.

To ensure that participant needs are accommodated and that participants feel heard, quality assessments of the workshops will be conducted. The quality assessments are adapted from workshop assessment criteria by Thoring et al. (2020), see further definition under the Quality Assurance chapter. The participants will be surveyed after each workshop session for feedback. One workshop-series for a given group will be divided into two sessions, and the following sessions will be adapted to their feedback. Furthermore, the participants will be able to provide feedback on the requirements before they are finalized.

3.2. Execution and Duration

10 workshops with 3-8 participants are planned for this study. Workshop sizes will be small enough for everyone to have an opportunity to share insights and yet large enough to provide a diverse set of perspectives. The workshops will be conducted virtually on Teams as the participants are located in different countries. Mural will be used as a virtual whiteboard.

The workshops will be conducted in between December 2022 and April 2023. Feedback for the requirements will be gathered shortly after the final workshop. External quality assessments will be done in 2023, of which the Z-inspection will begin on February 23rd, 2023.

3.3. Overview of Study plan

1. Utilize a patient/user journey and stakeholder mapping.
2. 10 workshops will be conducted with VALIDATE stakeholders.
Each workshop will be in the format of 2 sessions x 2-hours.
At the end of each workshop session participants will answer feedback surveys. The following sessions will be improved based on feedback.
After each workshop session, a quality assessment of the workshop will be done by the investigators according to the criteria outlined under Quality Assurance Procedures.
The reflexivity journaling will start when the ethics committee application is submitted and continue during the study, especially before and after workshops are held.
3. Quantification and specification of requirements based on workshop outcomes.
The method used for this will be Planguage.
4. Get feedback on the specified requirements from stakeholders.
5. Revise the specified requirements based on feedback from participants.
6. Compare with Z-inspection results and expert assessments to assess the quality of workshop-elicited requirements.

3.4. Definition of End of Study

The end of study is when the last requirement definition is approved by the participants.

4. RECRUITMENT

4.1. Study Participants

The selection of participants is a purposive sample based on the VALIDATE personnel list. The selection will be done by the investigators of this project.

A diverse range of people will be impacted by the future use of the AI tool, from patients to engineers. The use of interdisciplinary teams when developing AI systems has been stressed as important by past research (Abdul et al., 2018; Zou & Schiebinger, 2018). The workshop participants will therefore have different academic backgrounds to represent the multitude of stakeholders. The participants are selected personnel from the VALIDATE research project. The personnel include, but are not limited to: Medical doctors, patient representatives, AI engineers, software developers, researchers, designers, and project administrators.

The study participants are distributed among Norway, Israel, Germany, Ireland, Spain, and Belgium.

Some participants will already have an established relation to the workshop facilitators. This might be a source of bias that might influence how the participants respond or behave. However, considering that the discussion of ethics might be a sensitive and complex topic, existing rapport might be beneficial to provide the safety needed to tell stories from experience and share honest opinions.

4.2. Number of Participants

Approximate number of participants is expected to be 40-60, since the current number of VALIDATE personnel is approximately 70 when including the investigators of this study.

4.3. Inclusion Criteria

- A person who is active personnel of the VALIDATE project or represents a relevant stakeholder. Active personnel are considered to be someone involved in at least one task of any work package in the VALIDATE research project.
- Each workshop will aim to have a mix of stakeholders with different academic backgrounds.
- Participant is willing and able to give informed consent for participation in the study.
- Participant can speak English.
- For clinicians, they should be neurologists or other health personnel with experience in stroke research and care.
- For patient representatives, they should be or represent patients who have had stroke or informal caregivers or be members of a stroke patient organization.
- Participant is available for virtual workshop participation through own device.

4.4. Exclusion Criteria

- VALIDATE personnel who are not available for any part of the workshops will be excluded from the workshops. However, they can still provide feedback to the elicited requirements from the workshop.

- VALIDATE personnel who have contributed to the design of the workshop study are ineligible as regular study participants. However, they can still observe the workshops and provide feedback to elicited requirements.

4.5. Informed Consent

The participant must sign and date the latest approved version of the Informed Consent form before any study specific activities are undertaken.

Written – and if requested additional verbal - versions of the Participant Information and Informed Consent will be presented to the participants detailing no less than: the exact nature of the study; what it will involve for the participant; the implications and constraints of the protocol; any risks involved in taking part. It will be clearly stated that the participant is free to withdraw from the study at any time for any reason without prejudice to future care, and with no obligation to give the reason for withdrawal.

The participant will be allowed as much time as wished to consider the information, and the opportunity to question the Investigator or other independent parties to decide whether they will participate in the study. Written Informed Consent will then be obtained by means of participant dated signature and dated signature of the person who presented and obtained the Informed Consent. The person who obtained the consent must be suitably qualified and experienced and have been authorised to do so by the Chief Investigator. A copy of the signed Informed Consent will be given to the participant. The original signed form will be retained at the study site.

4.6. Discontinuation/Withdrawal of Participants from Study

Each participant has the right to withdraw from the study at any time. (In addition, the Investigator may discontinue a participant from the study at any time if the Investigator considers it necessary for any reason including:

- Ineligibility (either arising during the study or retrospectively having been overlooked at screening)
- Significant protocol deviation
- Significant non-compliance with study requirements
- Withdrawal of Consent

The withdrawal from the study will mean that their identifiable personal data such as name, contact information, and institution will be deleted from the participant list. The transcripts that are already de-identified will be kept since identification of the participant is not possible any more. Withdrawn participants might be replaced by colleagues from the same institution or in the case of patient representatives, others with similar backgrounds.

The reason for withdrawal by researcher (and by participant, if this information is volunteered) will be recorded in a study file.

5. DATA COLLECTION

5.1. Workshops

Workshops will be conducted online using a virtual conferencing tool. Workshops will mainly be facilitated by research team member Cathrine Bui, who has previous experience with holding workshops or the chief investigator Vince Madai, or yet unnamed study personnel. We will use observations, screenshots of the virtual boards on an online whiteboard tool, and field notes from workshops to collect data. The workshops will be recorded, and the conversations will be automatically transcribed verbatim using specialised software. These transcripts will be used as reference to more accurately define any ethics requirements that were not defined in Planguage in the workshops. Workshops will be scheduled depending on the participants' availability.

Workshops will be divided into two sessions. In the first session, the focus will be on doing group storytelling by the participants. Participants will receive prompts to tell these stories. See more below. Based on the stories, participants will brainstorm and identify relevant ethical issues.

In the second session, the participants will prioritize the different issues and choose one issue to focus on in the workshop. This issue will then be further defined and translated into Planguage.

In the following, these two phases are described in more detail.

5.1.1. Group Storytelling in Workshop Session 1

Structured storytelling is an agile technique that depends on involving the targeted beneficiaries (or end-users) more fully in elaborating project requirements through using their own stories (Pitula & Radhakrishnan, 2011). Storytelling is an easily accessible approach that does not require any high level of experience and skills to communicate with the participants and extract information or meaning from (Scott et al., 2013). These stories are analyzed and abstracted into sets of needs, goals, and constraints to serve as a primary input for achieving a project's goals and driving requirements from the bottom up (Pitula & Radhakrishnan, 2011). Structured storytelling prioritizes user needs foremost in driving requirements while it identifies contextual information that might otherwise be overlooked (Pitula & Radhakrishnan, 2011). This means that a more complete understanding of the problem could be obtained by integrating a bottom-up analysis with a conventional top-down approach (Pitula & Radhakrishnan, 2011).

Pitula & Radhakrishnan made a comparison between group storytelling and focus group interviews and mentioned the following features: Group storytelling could be similar to focus group interviews; in their specific case, the process involved four main steps: Identifying themes of interest; collecting stories rather than answers for prepared or semi-prepared questions; processing the stories to extract information; and modelling the extracted information (2011). However, group storytelling is more effective in eliciting more diverse information within less time (Pitula & Radhakrishnan, 2011). During focus group interviews, as a project may deal with more than one profession, it becomes difficult for the participant to answer direct questions that may not understand or feel intimidated as these questions may not be regarding their field. In this situation, Pitula and Radhakrishnan elaborated that group storytelling outweighs focus group interviews as the stakeholder will narrate their story and expert as a story away from the question-and-answer format (2011). This will lead to eliciting a wide range of points and experiences that might not be highlighted or explored when using question-and-answer format interviews.

As a result, Pitula and Radhakrishnan elaborated that group storytelling accommodates cross-professional differences; it impacts positively when several professionals' backgrounds are involved in a common project; their goals will reflect diverse issues and motivations that we may not consider when using methods rather than group storytelling (2011). Stakeholders from different professional fields will bring different perspectives and express themselves in different ways. All the appeared concerns and assumptions would be taken into consideration to map into the final project goal.

The first part of the workshops will therefore be group storytelling. One of the aims of using group storytelling is to let the participants jog each other's memory to think of additional potential ethical issues or relevant past experiences (Pitula & Radhakrishnan, 2011). Since most of the participants, and especially the doctors, have limited knowledge about what AI ethics entails, a group storytelling exercise where participants outline different scenarios in their work might help highlight nuances and details that otherwise would not have been mentioned if they were asked a more direct question about ethics.

5.1.2. Defining and Quantifying Requirements Using Language in Workshop Session 2

In the second workshop session, the participants will be presented with a pre-selected set of ethical issues, mostly based on the first workshop. The pre-selected set will be chosen by the research investigators. The participants will then prioritize the top 10 ethical issues they deem to be the most relevant and important for the project. They will further choose one issue to focus on in the session.

This issue will then be further defined and translated into Planguage. This issue should be what the participants think is the most critical issue for the AI-tool. Translated into Planguage involves:

1. Defining the **stakeholders** of the issue. Stakeholders can be people, institutions, or constraints (e.g., regulations).
2. Defining the **scale** and **parameters** of the issue. How will progress in solving the issue be measured? Which parts need to be present? What needs to be increased or decreased in order for the issue to be resolved?
3. Defining the **wish** of the participants. What number do the participants wish for the scale to be on? The wish is the ideal "dream" of the participants. This will later be adjusted by the investigators to fit within the constraints of the project so that it becomes a **goal**. The goal will then be a commitment that the project works towards achieving.

After the workshops, the investigators will converge the different ethical issues from different workshops and translate the ones that were not defined in the workshops into Planguage. The set of ethical issues and goals will then be sent to participants for comments and feedback; edited according to feedback; and finalized.

6. DATA MANAGEMENT

6.1. Access to Data

Direct access will be granted to authorised representatives from the Sponsor or host institution for monitoring and/or audit of the study to ensure compliance with regulations.

6.2. Data Recording and Record Keeping

Audio recordings from the workshops will be stored on secure Charité servers until transcriptions have been made and reviewed for errors.

We will use specialised software for automated transcription and then go through the transcript to check for errors. Additional transcribing will be done with MAXQDA.

Participant contact details (email address), qualification level, and information on the use of QUEST services will be stored on secure Charité servers until the end of the project. Once the project is completed, these data will be deleted. Participants' workshop-related data – in this case, the pseudonymized workshop transcripts and virtual boards – will be stored for at least 10 years in accordance with Charité's Good Scientific Practice statutes. Storage beyond this time frame is sought for two reasons: (i) for the purpose of long-term re-use (ii) to allow for long-term comparisons.

7. DATA ANALYSIS

7.1 Description of Analytical Methods

7.1.1 Content Analysis

Content analysis is a general term that encompasses a variety of text analysis strategies (Powers & Knapp, 2010). In this approach, it is possible to examine large amounts of text by coding and thematizing it, in order to identify trends and patterns, such as how words are used, the frequency of their use, and the context where these words were used. (Grbich, 2012; Mayring, 2004; Pope et al., 2006). It is appropriate to use content analysis when trying to answer questions such as: What concerns do people have about an event? How do people decide whether to use a service or procedure? (Ayres, 2007). The content analysis technique can be used to quantitatively analyze data while simultaneously analyzing it qualitatively (Grbich, 2012); data is codified and quantitative counts of the codes are interpreted using a descriptive approach in content analysis (Downe-Wamboldt, 1992; Morgan, 1993).

It is possible to divide the content analysis into multiple phases.

- Preparation is the first phase, which involves immersing oneself in the data and getting a sense of the whole, selecting the units of analysis, and deciding whether manifest content (developing categories) or latent content (developing themes) will be analyzed (Vaismoradi et al., 2013). In developing a category, the aim is to provide a descriptive level of content and, therefore, express the manifest content of the text. Whereas in developing a theme, the aim is to dig deeply and express the latent content of the text. (Vaismoradi et al., 2013)
- The second phase is the organizing phase. In this phase, open coding and categorization are done, codes are grouped under higher order headings, and a general description of the research topic is derived through generating top-level categories and subcategories (Vaismoradi et al., 2013).

- The last phase is called reporting, where models, conceptual systems, conceptual maps, and storylines are used to report the results of the analyzing process (Vaismoradi et al., 2013).

7.1.2 Concept Mapping

Concept mapping is a method for structuring qualitative data using a framework (Brightman, 2003). It can be used to explore causal relationships, other relationships, and highlight the consequences of actions for different categories, ideas, or variables in the data. During the map-building process, the map builder must answer the question: how are these concepts related? (Brightman, 2003)

Concept maps are made up of many elements: A "concept" describes a class of things as a whole and is commonly framed with rectangles when drawn on a concept map. A "proposition", which helps to organize the data, is a statement or assertion that integrates at least two concepts and two connecting words to make a meaningful statement. To deepen a concept map, new links between different domains of data are often needed, and hence, mapped information is often enhanced by cross-links. Cross-links provide links between the different "domains" of the map. A "domain": a branch that focuses on a certain aspect of the issue being considered). (Brightman, 2003)

An important feature of the concept map is its hierarchical structure, with the most general and inclusive statements at the top and the most particular and detailed statements positioned below. In most cases, the top-level statement is the map's subject, and from there, the relationship between a concept and another concept may have more than one link. (Brightman, 2003)

Cross-links provide links between the different "domains" of the map (a domain is a "branch" of the map which deals with one particular aspect of the issue being considered). Cross-links often provide new insights into the information being mapped. (Brightman, 2003)

7.1.3 Planguage

The use of methods for quantifying requirements is important in the field of AI ethics because what is not measured is more difficult to improve. Quantified metrics for whether a goal of auditability or trustworthiness has been met will increase transparency and accountability. When defining vague high-level principles into something quantified and measurable, it can bring to light the unsaid issues that need to be discussed. This will hopefully bring forth a concrete definition that will provide a shared language for future discussions and to a clear path of action. This study will look at the method Planguage for this purpose.

A Planning Language or its shortened term, *Planguage*, is an effective interactive tool to quantify a result from a process or work (Gilb, 1989). Planguage helps in defining the expected result to customers or several stakeholders by translating the text and words to measures and numbers. Tse and Kahlon described how Planguage enhances the interrelationship qualities between people, processes, and technology such as AI (2013).

The creator of Planguage, Thomas Gilb, writes that the main objective of any project is to improve an existing system (1989). Planguage tools can be applied to clarify the requirements analysis of IT projects in many different fields, such as managing projects and enforcing the quality of the healthcare system (Tse & Kahlon, 2013). Tse & Kahlon also stated that the main problem of any IT-related projects or literature that is applied in fields such as healthcare, is the difficulties that may face the stakeholders

such as health workers to understand the analysis of these IT systems or the expected results (2013). Also, they described how Planguage was an effective tool that led a healthcare IT project to be successfully delivered and how this method enabled the project to address stakeholder values and viewpoints more visually and explicitly (Tse & Kahlon, 2013). Gilb stated that Planguage is mainly a result specification language, which means its main objective is to show the clarity of a project (1989).

A sample of how a measurable requirement might look like in the Planguage format is the following:

% of the **[Information Type]** are available through **[Release Type]** every **[Time Interval]** to relevant **[Stakeholders]** so that they can **[Action]**.

Where the parameters are defined as:

[Information Type]: Assumptions of the AI-tool, Limitations of the AI-tool, Operating protocols, Data, Meta-Data, Methods used for data collection, Methods used for data processing, Methods used for data labelling, Methods for developing the AI algorithm.

[Release Type]: Publication, Internal Documentation, FAQs, Translated FAQs.

[Time interval]: Year.

[Stakeholders]: System Evaluators, Government Regulators, Auditors, Marginalized Populations, Doctors, Patients.

[Action]: Identify Errors, Conduct Effective Oversight, Understand How to Use the AI Tool.

This would mean that there would be different sentence versions of that requirement when progress has been made, for example:

10% of the **operating protocols** is available through **internal documentation** every **year** to relevant **system evaluators** so that they can **identify errors**.

70% of the **limitations of the AI-tool** are available through **FAQs** every **year** to relevant **doctors** so that they can **understand how to use the AI tool**.

Note, that the definitions of these measures and numbers are somewhat subjective, they are opinion-based ideas about how something should be measured and when this measure is fulfilled. For instance, the number of “information types that should be available” is defined by the stakeholder group, it is not based on objective datapoints from sources such as wide-spread surveys.

7.2 Data Analysis Process

First, content analysis will be used to analyse the transcriptions of the audio files from the workshops, with a focus on identifying ethical issues. The analysis for deriving ethical issues will focus on the group storytelling part as it is expected that in other parts of the workshop, the identified ethical issues will be sufficiently documented in the field notes or the virtual workshop board.

In the second phase of the content analysis, relational ethics will be used as a lens for the open coding to find additional relevant aspects (Birhane, 2021; Dignum, 2022). Relational ethics looks at ethics with a focus on relationships, interdependence, and connectedness (Birhane, 2021).

The analysis will partially be inductive and deductive. We are doing a deductive analysis based on the EU ethics guidelines and relational ethics. The inductive coding will be done to identify additional ethics issues.

In the final phase of content analysis, concept mapping will be used to create an overview of the connections between themes, categories, and codes. The concept mapping will focus on mapping the central ethical issues and requirements.

After the ethical issues have been identified and prioritized, they will be defined into requirements in plain language. After that, they will be translated into Planguage. Some of the prioritization of ethical issues will be done by the participants during the workshops. The requirements will finally be sent to workshop participants and revised according to their feedback.

According to Ørngreen, it makes a difference whether the data analysts were originally present in the workshops (2017). The data analysis will therefore be performed by the investigators who will also be present in the workshops.

8. QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCEDURES

The principles defined for evaluating workshops by Thoring et al. (2020) will be adapted to assess the success of the workshops. Each workshop will be assessed using these principles shortly after each has ended.

The following aspects will be measured:

1. The variety and relevance of participants' opinions and ideas.
 2. The workshop agenda and timing. Both the participants' experience of the workshop and how it was to facilitate it; whether there should be any practical improvements regarding the facilitation.
 3. The workshop templates, specifically the use of Planguage as methods for concretization.
 4. Quality of the workshop outcome, which is the requirement quantified in the workshop.
- Aspect 1 will be evaluated using the audio recordings and an artefact analysis of the virtual workshop board. The aspect will be measured by 1) counting the number of identified issues and 2) how the issues are distributed across and outside of the different EU principles. A relevant issue is an ethical challenge or dilemma that will be turned into a requirement using one of the quantification methods.
 - Aspects 2 and 3 will be measured using short surveys, observation, field notes, and an artefact analysis of the virtual workshop board.
 - Aspect 4 will be evaluated by doing an artefact analysis of the elicited requirements. The analysis will be scored independently by 3 research team members.

Table of Adapted Workshop Evaluation Principles					
Nr	Aspect	Observation & Notes	Audio Recording	Survey	Artefact Analysis
1	The variety and relevance of participants' opinions and ideas.		Medium suitability.		Artefact analysis of the virtual workshop board. Medium suitability.
2	The workshop agenda and timing.	Good suitability.		Participants will answer survey on their experience of the workshops at the end of each workshop session. Medium suitability	Artefact analysis of the virtual workshop board. Medium suitability.
3	The workshop templates.	Good suitability.		Good suitability.	Good suitability.
4	Quality of the workshop outcome.	Medium suitability.			Artefact analysis of the elicited requirements. Good suitability.

Table and suitability levels adapted from Thoring et al. (2020)

8.1 Expert Assessment

Three ethicists in the field will be identified to review and compare the outcome of our workshops. The experts will be given information about VALIDATE and will be asked to independently come up with ethics requirements for the project. The expert assessments are then compared to our results and a score will be applied by the experts for the comparison.

The requirements from the expert assessments will be compared to the workshop-elicited requirements based on these criteria:

- Number of recommendations.
- The level of recommendations (high- or low-level) and how actionable they are.
- Overlaps and distinctions.

- Whether the expert recommendations have identified requirements outside of the EU principles for Trustworthy AI.

The experts will be chosen on the following criteria:

- The experts should have specialized knowledge on AI and ethics.
- The experts have published at least one research paper on the topic of AI and ethics OR had at least one year of practical experience with implementing AI ethics in the industry or government.
- The experts are not a part of the VALIDATE personnel.
- The experts have no conflicts of interest.
- The group of experts should have a diversity in gender, ethnicity, and cultural background.
- The experts are English-speaking and should have a good understanding of European ethical norms and values.

8.2 Z-inspection Assessment

Z-inspection assessments are done by an interdisciplinary team of experts to perform a comprehensive audit or assessment of any AI tool (Zicari et al., 2021). Z-inspection assessment results outline the trustworthiness of AI tools mainly based on the EU definition of Trustworthy AI and is suitable for healthcare applications (European Commission, 2019; Zicari et al., 2021). Given the validation level of the Z-inspection approach we can consider it a gold-standard methodology with regards to outcome that has, however, limited practical applicability as it involves dozens of experts and takes usually up to 6 months to perform. It can thus serve as external validation for our workshop results. Within the VALIDATE study, in a specific task on February 23rd, 2023, a Z-inspection assessment of VALIDATE will be performed. We will utilize these results to compare them to the final outcomes of the workshop results.

8.3 Reflexivity Journal

The lack of diversity and prevalent unconscious biases in AI is often quoted as some of the reasons why AI algorithms turn out biased (Leavy, 2018; West et al., 2019). It is therefore important that researcher's bias is acknowledged and reported in a transparent manner.

However, what is considered ethical or trustworthy is usually subjective and contextually determined. Therefore, we choose to be transparent about our potential biases instead of aiming for an "imagined objectivity" that is common in positivist research (D'Ignazio & Klein, 2020). Rather than simply viewing researcher subjectivity as a threat to validity, this study aims to use a reflexive approach to take advantage of our positional perspectives and lived experiences.

In this study, reflexivity means to examine and take responsibility for how we as investigators and workshop facilitators might influence the participants and our interpretation of the workshop dialogue (Berger, 2015). We will use reflexivity journals to self-monitor how our biases might affect the research outcomes.

Reflexivity is widely used in research within social work, but it is not commonly used in research in medicine or public health (Dodgson, 2019). Considering that this study focuses on the trustworthiness and auditability of an AI system, as opposed to its medical outcomes, the research might resemble more of a study in social work, more than traditional medical studies. Furthermore, reflexivity is an established practice to ensure rigor and quality for qualitative researchers, and is referred to as the “gold standard for determining trustworthiness (Dodgson, 2019, p. 220).

Cohen & Crabtree state that a sign of good qualitative research is to use reflexive processing methods to report relevant preconceptions (2008). In this study, the researchers will therefore write reflexivity journals for this purpose.

Topics to be considered in the journal might include (but are not limited to): Values, political and professional beliefs, knowledge, biases, social position, immigration status, sexual orientation, gender, age, nationality, ethnicity, language, affiliation, personal preferences, personal experiences, and emotional responses to participants (Berger, 2015; Dodgson, 2019).

9. ETHICAL AND REGULATORY CONSIDERATIONS

9.1 Approvals

The protocol, informed consent form, and participant information sheet will be submitted to an appropriate Research Ethics Committee (REC) for written approval.

The Investigator will submit and, where necessary, obtain approval from the above parties for all substantial amendments to the original approved documents.

9.2 Participant Confidentiality

The study staff will ensure that the participants’ anonymity is maintained. The participants will be identified only by a participant ID number on all trial documents and any electronic database. All documents will be stored securely and only accessible by study staff and authorised personnel. The study will comply with the Data Protection Act, which requires data to be anonymised as soon as it is practical to do so.

9.3 Other Ethical Considerations

The power imbalance between the researchers as workshop facilitators and the workshop participants can lead to an unwanted biasing and influence on the participants (de Jager et al., 2017). Continuous reflection on decision-making processes, communication, and participant experiences are needed to mitigate this power imbalance (de Jager et al., 2017). Although researchers’ positionality can be used as a strength to increase safety and understanding, it is important in action research that the researchers do not push their views onto the participants (Berger, 2015).

Leading questions and assumptions about the views of participants should be avoided (de Jager et al., 2017). It is important that the members of the research team find a valid and ethical balance between

their own personal opinion and the opinion of participants when defining the requirements and making prioritizations where ethical tensions arise (Ørngreen & Levinsen, 2017). Research team members need to develop an awareness of one's own positionality, biases, and assumptions, and take this into account when analysing the data (de Jager et al., 2017; Dodgson, 2019).

The representation of experience is limited to the VALIDATE personnel or other relevant stakeholders that might be identified along the way (de Jager et al., 2017). The use of workshops and group storytelling might both empower participants to tell stories that might be difficult to tell, but it can also lead to peer pressure or self-censoring (de Jager et al., 2017). Stories might be highly sensitive in nature since it might be related to personal experiences related to stroke.

9.4 Funding and Expenses

Funding for the study comes from the Horizon Europe VALIDATE EU research project. No travel expenses are expected as the workshops will be held virtually.

9.5 Publication Policy

The Investigators will be involved in reviewing drafts of the manuscripts, abstracts, press releases and any other publications arising from the study. Authors will acknowledge that the study was funded by Horizon Europe. Authorship will be determined in accordance with the ICMJE guidelines and other contributors will be acknowledged.

9.6 Researcher disclosure

Chief investigator & workshop facilitator: Dr. med. Vince Madai

Credentials: M.D. (Charité Berlin), Ph.D. in Medical Neuroscience (Charité Berlin), M.A. in Medical Ethics (Mainz University)

Gender: Cis-male.

Nationality: German

Experience and training: Trustworthy AI is the main research focus of the CI. Has published on this topic and conducts active research on many facets of trustworthy AI. Regularly holds speeches on the ethical challenges of AI.

Relationship with participants: Participating in the same EU research consortium with the VALIDATE personnel. Knows some participants from a former EU study (Precise4Q). Has published papers with several consortium members.

Other characteristics: Two mother tongues (Hungarian and German). English is third language. Family history of stroke.

Investigator & main workshop facilitator: Cathrine Bui

Credentials: B.Sc. in Information Technology, M.Sc. in Informatics from the University of Oslo.

Occupation at the time of study: AI ethics consultant at Bui Consulting and research fellow at Charité.

Gender: Cis-female.

Nationality: Norwegian.

Experience and training: Has conducted a qualitative master's thesis project study on gender bias in AI. Written a master's thesis and scientific poster on gender bias in AI. 1 year practical experience from the industry as AI ethics consultant, workshop facilitator, and speaker. Has conducted workshops with design thinking methods since 2018.

Relationship with participants: Participating in the same EU research consortium with the VALIDATE personnel. Have met some of the VALIDATE personnel during virtual consortium meetings. In a Norwegian ethics group with one of the participants.

Other characteristics: Of Vietnamese family heritage. English is third learned language after Vietnamese and Norwegian. Has a family history of stroke. Has interest in the research topic because of past work in gender equality and is personally affected by sexist and racist AI systems.

Investigator & workshop facilitator: Luis Miguel Lopez-Ramos

Credentials: B. Sc. Telecommunication Engineering, M. Sc. Multimedia and Communications, Ph. D. Multimedia and Communications

Gender: Cis- Male

Nationality: Spanish

Experience and training: Has conducted research in explainable time-series modelling based on ANN.

Written a conference article about the potential of automated machine learning in healthcare.

Relationship with participants: Participating in the same EU research consortium with the VALIDATE personnel. Has met some of the VALIDATE personnel during consortium meetings.

Other characteristics: Originally from Spain. English is second language.

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AMENDMENT HISTORY

Amendment No.	Protocol Version No.	Date issued	Author(s) of changes	Details of Changes made